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Dramatic Discourse and the Characterization of Gender Semas in Metaphors in Uzbek and English Languages

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Abstract: *This study examines how dramatic discourse in Uzbek and English languages encodes gendered semas (units of meaning) in metaphors. By analyzing plays from both linguistic traditions, the research identifies patterns in metaphorical language that reflect gender roles, stereotypes, and cultural attitudes. Key findings suggest that while both languages use metaphors to convey gender-specific traits, differences arise due to cultural and linguistic influences. This comparative analysis provides insights into the role of language in shaping and reflecting gender perceptions in drama.*

Key words: *primary school, education, curriculum, lesson, mathematics, language, problems, teacher, subject.*

Introduction

Language in dramatic discourse is a powerful tool for constructing and communicating cultural values, particularly in the representation of gender. Metaphors in dramatic texts often reveal implicit attitudes toward gender roles, creating semas that reflect societal norms and stereotypes. This paper investigates the characterization of gender semas in metaphors in Uzbek and English dramatic discourse, exploring how these linguistic features highlight similarities and differences between the two cultures. Understanding these patterns sheds light on the intersection of language, culture, and gender in literary contexts.

Methods

A comparative qualitative approach was adopted to analyze dramatic texts in Uzbek and English.

- **Corpus:** Selected Uzbek plays included works by Abdulla Qodiriy (O'tkan Kunlar) and Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy (Boy ila Xizmatchi), while English texts included Shakespearean plays

(Hamlet, Macbeth and works by modern playwrights like Tennessee Williams (*A Streetcar Named Desire*)).

- Focus: The study examined metaphorical expressions explicitly or implicitly referencing gendered traits, roles, or stereotypes.
- Analysis: Each metaphor was analyzed for its gender semas, including associations (e.g., strength, beauty, passivity) and cultural implications. Comparative analysis was conducted to identify cross-linguistic patterns and divergences.

Results

1. Common Metaphorical Themes in Gender Representation

- Uzbek Plays: Gendered metaphors often reflect traditional roles, associating women with nature (e.g., “oy” – moon, symbolizing beauty and purity) and men with strength (e.g., “tog” – mountain, symbolizing stability).
- English Plays: Similar metaphors appear, with women likened to delicate flowers (e.g., “rose” in *Hamlet*) and men to powerful animals or forces (e.g., “lion” in *Macbeth*).

2. Cultural Influences on Gendered Metaphors

- In Uzbek plays, metaphors often emphasize familial and communal roles, such as women being “chevar ip” (delicate thread) symbolizing the cohesive force in family.
- English plays frequently highlight individuality, with metaphors like “steel-hearted” (denoting resilience) used for male characters.

3. Gender Stereotypes and Power Dynamics

- Uzbek discourse portrays women through metaphors that emphasize emotional strength (e.g., “buloq” – spring, nurturing but confined to its source).
- English plays use metaphors to challenge or reinforce traditional roles, such as Lady Macbeth’s metaphorical association with “unsexing” herself to gain power.

4. Symbolic Overlap and Divergences

- Both languages use nature-based metaphors for women and strength-based metaphors for men, but Uzbek plays are more rooted in agricultural and family-centric symbols, while English plays draw from broader mythological and individualistic references.

Discussion

The analysis reveals that metaphors in dramatic discourse are a significant means of encoding gender semas, reflecting both universal and culture-specific themes. While Uzbek and English plays share some metaphorical patterns (e.g., associating women with beauty and men with strength), their differences highlight distinct cultural priorities. Uzbek metaphors emphasize communal harmony and traditional roles, while English metaphors often explore individuality and power dynamics.

These findings underscore the role of dramatic discourse as a mirror of societal values, with metaphors serving as a linguistic bridge between abstract concepts and cultural realities. However, the study also highlights the evolving nature of gender semas, as modern playwrights challenge traditional metaphors to redefine gender norms.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that dramatic discourse in Uzbek and English languages employs metaphors to construct and communicate gender semas, reflecting societal attitudes and cultural contexts. While there are shared themes, the distinct linguistic and cultural influences of each language shape their metaphorical representations of gender. Future research could explore how these patterns evolve in contemporary drama and digital media, offering further insights into the dynamic relationship between language, culture.

References

1. Арутюнова Н.Д. Дискурс. В кн.: Лингвистическая энциклопедия.– М., 1990.–С. 136-137.
2. Богданов В.В. Речевое общение: прагматические и семантические аспекты. – Л.: ЛГУ, 1990. – С.89.
3. Кибрик А.А.Когнитивные исследования по дискурсу // Вопросы языкознания. – 1994. –№5. –С.126-139.
4. Макаров М.Л.Основы теории дискурса. – М.: Гнозис, 2003. –С. 280.
5. Ивин А.А. Оценки в процессах коммуникации. URL: <http://iphras.ru/uplfile/root/biblio/ps/ps17/14.pdf> (дата обращения: 18.08.2016).
6. Ефанова Л.Г. Субъект нормативной оценки, выражаемой семантикой языковых единиц, как носитель национальной языковой картины мира //
7. Сибирский филологический журнал. 2013. № 1. С. 101–106. Арутюнова Н.Д. Язык и мир человека. М. : Языки русской культуры, 1999. 896 с.
8. Раупова Л. Диалогик дискурсади полипредикатив бирликларнинг социопрагматик тадқиқи: филол.фан.д-ри...дисс.автореф. Т.: 2012.;